

THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING MATHEMATICS THROUGH ICT

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Annotation: This article describes the ways to improve methods and algorithms of the automated control of knowledge, approaches to the establishment and effective functioning of electronic teaching complexes, which include tests of a new generation, and their use is not limited control purpose only.

Keywords: Internet, information and communication technologies, assessment, quality control, education, the level of educational achievements, computer testing, monitoring, university

Building an effective education system that is capable to form a creative person who is ready to work in a fundamentally new information environment of the XXI century puts on the agenda the problem of the active introduction of information technology in the learning process, the development of a unified educational information environment. This environment will bring together educational and scientific potential of leading universities and other educational institutions into a unified system. Moreover, it is very important to use the latest smart achievements unhesitatingly spread into all spheres of life, as the application area of their use has become much more diverse. Recently, universities in Russia have paid great attention to the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in teaching mathematical and other subjects. Using these technologies provides a number of advantages in the field of information technology.

Using modern computer technology students have the opportunity to read the most recent teaching materials created in the departments, whereas the publication of the paper takes a long time and these texts could become obsolete or lose relevance. It should also be borne in mind that in many cases the number of textbooks in a library is insufficient or some books are not available. Computerization is one of bases of modernization of modern education. The use of information technologies in the educational process certainly has many advantages [1]. Modern technologies enable the diversification of the study of mathematics. Using presentations, animations and video material a professor can more clearly explain a new topic. Presentation slides significantly reduce the time that it takes to explain the material. Due to the use of information technologies in a classroom a teacher can show the fragments of educational and scientific films, tables, graphs and diagrams, animations of mathematical processes and phenomena, the work of technical devices and experimental setups, photos and so on. The use of almost all types and forms of educational information resources in educational practice substantially improves the quality of visual and audio information, it becomes brighter, more colorful, more dynamic. Modern multimedia technologies have tremendous opportunities. In addition, the use of electronic educational resources and advantages of modern telecommunications in training radically changes the way of creating visual and audio information. The traditional visual learning means refer to a specific object. Now dynamic interpretation of the essential properties of not only real world objects, but also scientific laws, theories, concepts and so on becomes possible with the computer and telecommunication technologies. The use of modern technology enables one to make any activity more visible, work with various information, such as sound, text, photos and video. However, some teachers overuse these opportunities, justifying it by the fact that a modern student is not inspired by narration and lectures alone. It is important to remember that information technologies should complement the material rather than replace it. Technology has changed beyond recognition, but the core values remain the same in education.

Sometimes it seems that information technology brings to the educational process only positive things. Of course, in most cases it is true, but there are two sides of every coin. Probably there is no such a teacher who does not understand that the use of the computer in a classroom is not just a fad. Obviously, the use of modern equipment, software, electronic educational resources helps one to conduct lessons more easily and make them more interesting. But one should not forget that the information technology is not a cure-all, but a good learning tool in the hands of a wise teacher. Their use should be thoughtful, reasonable and competent. Only the talent and skill of a teacher will find a middle ground in the use of information technology. The purpose of this study is to develop modern methods and new scientific and methodological approaches to learning mathematics, using innovative technologies of students by universities, as well as the experimental confirmation of the pedagogical usefulness of the proposed methods.

less of the proposed methods. The analysis of modern scientific and methodical literature enables the selecting of the main areas of ICT use in education [2].

1. Information and methodological support. This area provides a qualitatively new level of access to a virtually unlimited volume of scientific and methodological information.

2. The means of organization and management of the educational process, which consists in determining the content and sequence of the presentation of learning content, record keeping and evaluation of students' work.

3. The means of improving the psychological and pedagogical conditions of educational activity, which creates opportunities of independent choice of the priorities, forms and learning pace for students.

4. The means of communication, which gives students opportunities to communicate with teachers, other members of the educational process regardless of location.

5. The means of modeling, automation of the experiment and analyzing the results. Modelling of processes and phenomena, especially fleeting and inaccessible ones to direct observation, makes it possible to study them. Automation accelerates

experimental studies of mathematical parameters measurement processes, accumulation and processing of information and frees up time for other learning activities.

6. Means of automation control and correction processes of learning outcomes, testing and diagnostics. Obtaining timely information about each student enables the use of a differentiated approach to the learning process and ensures the provision of necessary methodological assistance.

7. The means for teaching and scientific and research activities of students and teachers. Information technologies provide the performance of training and research projects.

Quality training of highly qualified specialists in modern conditions requires from students not only basic knowledge, but also fundamental knowledge for understanding principles of advanced technologies. This implies an increase of the actual volume of educational material and reducing the number of classroom hours. To solve such a complex problem is possible only with the use of modern information technology. Different training systems with using information and communication technologies, including distance learning, have become part of life. With many similar features and capabilities they, nevertheless, have their own characteristics depending on the specifics of subjects and requirements for learning outcomes. The implementation of competence-based approach in accordance with the requirements of the federal state educational standards of higher professional education provides the widespread use of active and interactive technologies of lessons, contributing to the accumulation of professional skills of students, and a significant increase of the volume of students' self-study in the learning process. Improving the quality of teaching, the quality of training is one of the main problems of the functioning of any educational system. In order to work effectively to improve the quality of training a teacher must have reliable information about students' achievement level. In the context of mass education in the modern university and the increasing volume of work, especially increasing number of students per teacher, regular receiving such information about each student becomes problematic.

In connection with the requirements of the new federal state educational standards of higher professional education it is very important to create new electronic teaching materials. They should contain tests of a new generation (competency test, practical skills, and others). Moreover, their use should not be limited only by assessment. Increasing the potential of test technologies for training, creating special thematic and other training test systems would be beneficial for a more productive organization of independent work of students. Testing has extensive experience of applying in education system. The use of information technology in the learning process leads to the search for new opportunities in diagnostic activities. One important area in this respect is the general approbation and implementation of computer-based testing. Problems of computer control of knowledge are usually considered in two aspects: technical and methodical. Methodical aspects include planning and organization of the controls, definition of the types of issues in tasks, making a set of questions and tasks for exam, the definition of evaluation criteria for each task and variant. Technical aspects include sample control tasks on the basis of the chosen approach, the choice and use of the system parameters of knowledge control, the choice of algorithms for the assessment of students' knowledge etc. The assessment of educational achievements of students is a part of quality assessment in university. Automation control is closely related to the automation of the entire educational process and provides feedback to the automated control systems of educational process.

Computer testing – an effective tool for monitoring and evaluation of students' knowledge Achieving high quality of education makes it necessary to use different methods of monitoring and assessment of knowledge and skills of students. Knowledge control is carried out in the traditional manner in the form of tests, examinations, written papers, reports, presentations, abstracts, computer presentations, etc. The measured results is a powerful stimulus to revise positions in the educational process, both for a student and a teacher. Test results make it possible for a teacher to quickly identify and resolve emerging students' difficulties and shortcomings in their own teaching. However, students sometimes do not agree with the assessment that a teacher has exposed. At the same time students adequately respond to the objective, reasonable

and transparent evaluation results obtained by the machine control. Therefore, computer testing can be identified specifically as one of the most effective forms of control of students' knowledge. The complexity of this process makes it relevant to computerize it. With the appropriate material-technical base (network computer classes) it is easy to organize preliminary (input) and the current test. The input testing of first-year students enables the determination of their residual after passing school exam. Subsequent testing makes it possible for a teacher to assess students' knowledge obtained after visiting lectures, carrying out practical and laboratory studies. At mathematical departments computer testing based on SCIENTIA system is widely used as a mean of monitoring and assessment. It is carried out at different stages of training in mathematics from the input to the final. This testing is not the only method of assessment; it is used together with other conventional methods, such as oral and written interviews, examinations, practical work, and exam.

The quality of education in general and mathematical education in particular is a multidimensional and multifaceted property of the result of training activities. It is determined by the variety of teaching and educational factors. Education system requires the creation of a unified information and educational and technological resource in the Internet based on resource integration and networking of various educational institutions. It will provide users with a wide range of different educational services, from access to materials of the distributed e-library to the opportunity to get education in any educational institution with virtual representation in the information educational environment. That may ultimately improve the quality of engineer training,

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